

Research on the Factors Affecting Leadership Style on Employee Satisfaction at Vietnamese Joint Stock Commercial Banks

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Abstract

In the increasingly competitive landscape of Vietnam's banking sector, a high-quality workforce plays a decisive role in ensuring sustainable development. One of the key factors affecting work performance and employee retention is leadership style. Both international and domestic studies have confirmed that leadership style significantly influences employee satisfaction, motivation, and organizational commitment. However, in Vietnam particularly within joint stock commercial banks research on the specific impacts of leadership styles on employee satisfaction remains limited and inconsistent. This study focuses on exploring and clarifying the factors through which leadership styles affect employee satisfaction in Vietnamese joint stock commercial banks, with the goal of contributing to more effective human resource management and organizational development.

Keywords: *Employee satisfaction, transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, laissez-faire leadership style.*

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Introduction

In the context of fierce competition in the banking industry today, the human factor plays an increasingly key role in creating sustainable competitive advantages for financial institutions. Employee satisfaction not only affects individual performance but also affects organizational productivity, engagement and retention rates of high-quality human resources. Meanwhile, leadership style is considered one of the important.

At Vietnamese joint stock commercial banks, the process of innovation, restructuring and digital transformation pressure is posing new requirements for the leadership team in building a positive working environment, promoting a spirit of cooperation and motivation. However,

there are still few systematic quantitative and qualitative studies on the relationship between leadership style and employee satisfaction in the banking sector in Vietnam. Factors that shape employee satisfaction.

The topic "Research on the factors affecting leadership style on employee satisfaction at Vietnamese joint stock commercial banks" has urgent theoretical and practical significance.

Research Overview

Rochelle Joy Belonio (2012) with the research titled: "The Effect of Leadership Style on Employee Satisfaction and Performance of Bank Employees in Bangkok". This study aimed to determine the impact of leadership style on employee job satisfaction and the impact of employee job satisfaction on their job

performance. A survey was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 400 respondents in the banking sector in Bangkok. The results showed that most bank employees, the majority of whom were women aged between 20 and 39, were dissatisfied. They had conflicting attitudes. Transformational leadership was found to have a positive impact on various aspects of employee job satisfaction. Transactional leadership was also found to positively affect many different aspects of job satisfaction. The same was observed for laissez-faire leadership. Employee job satisfaction was shown to have a positive impact on several aspects of employee job performance that were analyzed. It was found that leaders and managers who combined different leadership styles identified in the study in varying proportions produced positive outcomes when performing their leadership tasks. The proportion of these combined leadership styles depended on the nature of the situation they encountered in the workplace.

Ernest Obuobisa-Darko and Theresa Obuobisa-Darko (2015), "Leadership and Employee Satisfaction in the Ghanaian Banking Sector", *European Journal of Business and Management*. The study was conducted with the aim of investigating the relationship between leadership and employee satisfaction in the banking sector in Ghana. A three-part questionnaire was used for the research. The first part of the questionnaire collected demographic information of the respondents, the second part related to the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), while the third part concerned the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ). A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed to randomly selected respondents from both private and public banks in Accra, Ghana. Of these, 150 were returned, showing a response rate of 75%, and 140 of them were usable. The findings of the study revealed a positive relationship between leadership style and job satisfaction. The results also indicated that inspirational motivation (a form of transformational leadership), management-by-exception, and laissez-faire (forms of transactional leadership) had significant and positive effects on job satisfaction. Therefore, the leadership style of managers influences the job satisfaction of bank

employees, and managers are advised to demonstrate effective leadership capabilities.

Muhammad Asrar-ul-Haq and K. Peter Kuchinke (2016), "Impact of Leadership Styles on Employees' Attitude Towards Their Leader and Performance: Empirical Evidence from Pakistani Banks". This article reports the results of a study that examined the impact of managers' leadership styles on the performance of their subordinates. The effect of leadership style on employee job performance was explored theoretically and tested empirically in the study. The findings of this research revealed that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance outcomes. However, the laissez-faire leadership style showed a negative relationship with employee performance outcomes in terms of both effectiveness and employee satisfaction.

Estephan, Hanady (2021), "The Impact of Leadership Style on Employee Satisfaction: The Case of BLOM Bank and LGB Bank in Lebanon", Notre Dame University. Practical significance: This study helps supervisors understand what best suits their employees and what makes them satisfied. Additionally, it assists them in understanding the level of employee satisfaction, evaluating the attitudes and managerial approaches of managers, and possibly expanding this research to link its findings to both employee and overall bank performance. Originality/Value: This topic is a unique study conducted to compare BLOM Bank and LGB Bank, highlighting the importance of leadership style on employee satisfaction. The research focuses on how effective leadership styles impact employee satisfaction and thereby ensure the success and sustainability of the organization. and employee satisfaction.

Ketut I.R. Sudiardhita, Universitas Negeri Jakarta (2018), "The Effect of Compensation, Motivation of Employee and Work Satisfaction to Employee Performance at PT. BANK XYZ (Persero) Tbk", *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*. This study aimed to determine the impact of compensation, work motivation, and job satisfaction on the

performance of employees at PT. BANK XYZ (Persero) Tbk by using a quantitative method and path analysis technique. The population of this study consisted of non-managerial employees working at 24 branch offices within Regional Office Area I, covering the provinces of DKI Jakarta, West Java, and Banten, with a total of 2,547 employees. The research sample included 346 respondents. The study followed an explanatory research method to test a theory or hypothesis in order to support or refute it based on the research findings. The results of the study indicated that: Compensation had a positive and significant effect on work motivation. Compensation also had a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Work motivation positively and significantly affected job satisfaction. Compensation positively and significantly influenced employee performance. Work motivation had a positive and significant impact on employee performance. Job satisfaction also had a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Miss Richa Aryan & Dr. Amrinder Singh (2021), "Impact of Motivation and Recognition on Employee's Performance: A Study on Public and Private Sector Banks in Punjab and Haryana", *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management*. The study was conducted from September 2019 to March 2021 using Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory to test its validity within the cultural context of Punjab and Haryana. This research employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches, including: Secondary data analysis, Literature review, A longitudinal study based on data from the European Values Survey (EVS, 2019), A quantitative study based on survey responses, a qualitative focus through group discussions. The research findings identified 18 motivator factors and 5 hygiene (maintenance) factors influencing employee performance.

Shahriar Shakib (2024), "The Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction in Private Banks: A Study on Transformational and Transactional Leadership", *Research Square*. This study delves into the impact of leadership styles on employee performance and job satisfaction in private banks, focusing on examining transformational

and transactional leadership. Notable findings emerged, showing that transformational leadership, characterized by inspiration, motivation, and support, has a significant correlation with enhanced employee performance and increased job satisfaction among private bank employees. In contrast, transactional leadership, which emphasizes clear job expectations and compliance, demonstrated a more selective influence on specific aspects of performance but had limited impact on job satisfaction. These findings hold important implications for the operational strategies of private banks, suggesting that a blend of transformational leadership practices, combined with selective integration of transactional elements, can optimize employee performance and job satisfaction.

Research Methods

The study employed a survey method using a standardized MLQ-based questionnaire, adapted to suit the specific characteristics of the banking sector in Vietnam. The research sample consisted of 224 employees working at five major joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam. The collected data were processed using SPSS software, applying descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and multiple regression analysis to examine the impact of different leadership styles on employee satisfaction.

Although many domestic and international studies have addressed the relationship between leadership style and employee satisfaction, several critical research gaps still need to be clarified:

(1) Lack of in-depth research in the context of Vietnamese joint-stock commercial banks

Most previous studies were conducted in manufacturing enterprises, public organizations, or multinational corporations.

Vietnamese joint-stock commercial banks have unique characteristics in terms of organizational culture, control mechanisms, performance pressures, and manager–employee relationships, which require a more context-specific and practical research framework.

(2) Limited analysis of specific leadership styles

Many studies only consider leadership styles in general and do not delve into specific types such as transformational, transactional, supportive, or laissez-faire leadership.

There is a lack of evaluation regarding the distinct impact levels and comparative effectiveness of different leadership styles on various aspects of job satisfaction.

(3) Lack of comprehensive quantitative models incorporating multiple influencing factors

Existing studies often use simple models and rarely apply advanced techniques such as Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), multiple regression, or Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the relationship between leadership style and employee satisfaction.

(4) Lack of studies controlling for individual and organizational factors

Factors such as gender, age, tenure, and department are often not controlled in previous studies, potentially leading to biased assessments of variable relationships.

(5) Absence of research updated post-COVID-19 and during digital transformation

The working environment in the banking sector has significantly changed after the pandemic and in the era of digital transformation. Leadership has become increasingly crucial in maintaining employee satisfaction and motivation; however, few studies reflect this current reality.

These research gaps form the foundation for the study “Factors Affecting Leadership Style and Employee Satisfaction in Vietnamese Joint-stock Commercial Banks”, which aims to:

Provide specific empirical evidence within the banking sector.

Contribute to theoretical development and validate modern analytical models.

Propose suitable leadership style solutions tailored to the current context of Vietnamese enterprises.

Theoretical Basis

Concept of Leadership Style

According to Bass & Avolio (1994), leadership style is not only the personal behavior of the leader but also the expression of the values, beliefs and expectations that they convey to their subordinates.

According to Gary Yukl (2002), leadership is a social influence process in which leaders seek the voluntary participation of subordinates to achieve organizational goals.

According to Robbins & Judge (2013), “Leadership style is the way in which a leader influences others to achieve goals through directing, motivating and coordinating the activities of a group or organization.”

According to Furthermore, Ferman & Liden (1999), leadership style is the leader’s approach and method to direct and motivate employees to work towards achieving common goals.

In short, Leadership style is the sum of behaviors, ways of behaving and methods that leaders use in the process of managing, orienting, communicating and influencing subordinates to achieve the organization's goals.

Concept of Employee Satisfaction

According to Cranny et al. (1992), employee satisfaction is defined as a combination of emotional and cognitive responses of employees to their jobs based on comparing actual job performance with expected job performance.

According to Schemerhon (1993), employee satisfaction is expressed through emotional and affective responses to various aspects of an employee's job. The author focuses on employee satisfaction through job position, supervision by superiors, relationships with colleagues, job content, compensation and promotion, physical conditions of the working environment and organizational structure.

According to Career Addict (2020), employee satisfaction is defined as a combination of emotional and cognitive responses of employees towards their leaders in their work in the organization.

In short, employee satisfaction is the positive or negative feelings of employees towards their jobs and work environment. This is an important

factor reflecting the level of satisfaction with work-related needs, desires and expectations, and also affects employees' attitudes, performance and commitment to the organization.

Transformational Leadership Style

Transformational leadership is more like visionary leadership, in which leaders motivate their employees to exceed certain expectations (Hater & Bass, 1988; Doucet, Fredette, Simard, & Tremblay, 2015). A transformational leader usually leads his employees by providing them with a vision. This is a charismatic leader and tries to inspire people through his vision and charisma.

According to Rouche, Baker and Rose (1989) and Tajasom, Hung, Nikbin and Hyun, (2015), transformational leaders help their followers achieve the organization's goals and mission by working with and through them. They motivate their followers by influencing their beliefs, values, attitudes and behaviors.

Transactional Leadership Style

According to Smith, Eldridge, and DeJoy (2016), transactional leadership has been used as a corrective approach, and has two dimensions: contingent rewards; and management by exception (active and passive). Contingent rewards means that leaders use rewards and incentives to achieve desired outcomes from their followers.

In management by exception, leaders take corrective actions when problems occur that are beyond their control. It is also of two types: active management by exception and passive management by exception. Active management by exception suggests that the leader suggests anticipatory behavior. Leaders with a transactional leadership style try to solve problems before they have a chance to occur. In passive management by exception, the leader does not anticipate problems but takes action when problems occur.

Laissez-Faire Leadership Style

Leaders do not participate in decisions, avoid responsibility, do not provide clear direction and

leave employees to handle work completely independently, without control and support. They do not even use rewards or other tools to satisfy the needs of their followers. As a result, employees will feel dissatisfied, ineffective and unproductive.

Factors Affecting Leadership Style on Employee Satisfaction

According to researcher Nguyen Thanh Hoi (2014), leadership style in an organization is influenced by many factors: type of business or business environment, corporate culture, risks, internal conflicts, legal procedures. Among the above factors, the business environment is the first influential factor. Most leaders will apply the working style in the previous working environment to the current working environment. Because when working in the previous environment, the leader has professional habits and this is not easy to change. If working in a good and highly disciplined environment, however, the work is democratic or free, autocratic, the leader will have that leadership style.

According to Blanchard (2013), leadership style is influenced by many factors, the leader's personality is one of the factors that form a certain leadership style. Depending on their personality, each leader will shape their own style of leadership. The autocratic leadership style shows that the leader is confident, dares to think and take responsibility before the group. The leader is willing to listen to opinions, promote the creativity of employees, and will tend to have a democratic leadership style. In practice, many situations have arisen that require leaders to solve situations effectively and choose the appropriate leadership style.

From here it can be seen that, in an organization, the leadership style used is influenced by many different factors and can be adjusted through the process of training, learning and accumulation.

Research Hypothesis

Transformational leaders motivate their followers in such a way that it goes beyond rewards and exchanges. Transformational leadership theories provide evidence that when a leader uses a transformational leadership style, it

creates an emotional attachment of the subordinates or employees towards the leader. The quality of a transformational leader can be assessed by the impact the leader has on the followers.

To test the similar relationship in the context of Vietnam and the popular support of this idea, the following hypothesis is developed

H1. Transformational leadership style has a positive influence on employee satisfaction at Vietnam Joint Stock Commercial Bank

Transactional leadership focuses on exchanges between leaders and employees through rewards or punishments based on performance. This style emphasizes compliance with procedures and clear targets. Although this style helps maintain stability and effective control of work, many studies show that it has a moderate or mixed positive impact on employee satisfaction. When rewards and punishments are relied on alone, employees may feel pressured or lack motivation for creativity and personal growth.

To test the similar relationship in the context of Vietnam and the popular support of this idea, the following hypothesis is developed

H2. Transactional leadership style has a positive influence on employee satisfaction at Vietnamese joint stock commercial banks.

Laissez-faire leadership is a style in which the leader allows employees to make decisions and

act with little intervention or guidance. This is considered a weak leadership style in many situations, as the absence of leadership leads to inattention, lack of direction, and reduced job satisfaction among employees. Studies show that this style often has a negative impact on employee satisfaction, especially when the work environment requires constant coordination, supervision, and support from the leader.

To test the similar relationship in the context of Vietnam and the popular support of this idea, the following hypothesis is developed

H3. The laissez-faire leadership style has a negative impact on employee satisfaction at Vietnam joint stock commercial banks.

The Current State of the Impact of Leadership Style on Employee Satisfaction at Vietnam Joint Stock Commercial Bank

Frequency Statistics

The subordinates of 5 joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam were considered as the population.

The sample consisted of 224 subordinates from different branches and were selected by non-random purposive sampling technique.

The employees had worked for at least 6 months at the bank branch.

Table 1. Descriptive Frequency Statistics

Content	Classification	Quantity (N)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Female	144	64.29
	Male	70	31.25
Age	≤ 25 years	6	2.68
	26–35 years	193	86.16
	36–45 years	15	6.70
	≥ 46 years	0	0.00
Education	College	24	10.71
	University	187	83.48
	Postgraduate	2	0.89
Experience	Less than 1 year	13	5.80
	1–4 years	106	47.32
	5–8 years	62	27.68
	9 years or more	35	15.62

Source: Author's own compilation

The descriptive statistics table with a sample size of 224 employees from 5 joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam shows the following main characteristics:

The proportion of women in the study sample is majority, with 144 people (64.29%), compared to 70 men (35.71%).

This shows that the study sample has a gender bias, reflecting that the working environment in joint stock commercial banks currently has a higher number of female employees than male employees.

The age group of 26–35 years old accounts for an overwhelming proportion with 193 people (86.16%), showing that the workforce is mainly young employees, in the age of career development.

The age group of 36–45 years old accounts for only 7.01%, and ≥ 46 years old is completely absent from the sample, reflecting that the aging workforce has not appeared much in the surveyed banking industry.

The group of ≤ 25 years old accounts for 2.68%, showing that the number of new graduates is still limited.

The majority of employees have university degrees, accounting for 187 people (83.48%), reflecting the high demand for professional qualifications in the banking industry.

College degrees account for 11.27%, and 18 years or more (postgraduate) accounts for only

0.89%, reflecting the limited number of highly qualified personnel in the organization.

The group with 1–4 years of experience accounted for the largest proportion (106 people, equivalent to 47.32%), showing that most employees are in the stage of accumulating professional experience.

The group with 5–8 years accounted for 27.68%, while the group with 9 years or more accounted for only 15.63%, showing that the number of long-term employees is not large.

Notably, only 6.25% of employees have less than 1 year of experience, which shows that the rate of new employees is not high, or the organization has a fairly good level of personnel stability.

Preliminary Assessment of the Scale Using Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient

Transformational Leadership Style Scale

According to Table 2, the statistical result of Cronbach's Alpha test of the transformed variable has a value of 0.849, according to the theory, this Cronbach's Alpha value is satisfactory because it is higher than 0.6 and less than 0.95. However, the adjusted total correlation value of the observed variable CD7 is 0.168, which is smaller than the minimum of 0.3, so this observed variable is eliminated. Continue to run Cronbach's Alpha a second time after removing this variable.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha Test Results of Transformational Leadership Style Variable

Cronbach's Alpha		Number of variables			
0.849		7			
Variable	Items	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed
CD1	Leaders have a clear vision that inspires employees.	21.46	12.230	0.737	0.808
CD2	Leaders inspire employees to	21.47	12.540	0.707	0.814

	achieve common goals.				
CD3	Leaders build trust and respect in the organization.	21.47	12.917	0.673	0.819
CD4	Leaders encourage employees to overcome difficulties.	21.53	12.588	0.719	0.812
CD5	Leaders encourage creativity and innovation in work.	21.44	13.175	0.625	0.826
CD6	Leaders care about the needs and difficulties of each individual.	21.43	12.468	0.696	0.815
CD7	Leaders support employees when they encounter work problems.	21.60	15.488	0.168	0.891

Source: SPSS analysis results

According to Table 3, the statistical result of the Cronbach's Alpha test of the second transformed variable has a value of 0.891. According to the theory, the Cronbach's Alpha value must be higher than 0.6 and less than 0.95 to meet the requirements. The Cronbach's Alpha values if the variable is eliminated are all less than

0.891, so no observed variables are eliminated. The adjusted total correlation value shows that the observed variables all have values greater than the minimum level of 0.3. Therefore, this scale satisfies the reliability requirements and is included in the next step of the study.

Table 3. Results of the Second Cronbach's Alpha Test of Transformational Leadership Style

Cronbach's Alpha		Number of variables			
0.891		6			
Variable	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed
CD1	17.99	10.589	0.755	0.864	
CD2	18.00	10.908	0.718	0.870	
CD3	18.00	11.246	0.687	0.875	
CD4	18.06	10.948	0.732	0.868	
CD5	17.97	11.458	0.645	0.881	
CD6	17.96	10.795	0.716	0.871	

Source: SPSS analysis results

Transactional Leadership Style Scale

According to Table 6.4, the Cronbach's Alpha test result of the transaction variable has a value

of 0.822. According to the theory, the required Cronbach's Alpha value must be higher than 0.6 and less than 0.95, so the test value of the transaction variable has met the requirements. At the same time, the Cronbach's Alpha values if the variable is eliminated are all less than 0.822, so no observed variables are eliminated. The test

of the adjusted total correlation value of the variables all gave results greater than the minimum level of 0.3. Therefore, this scale satisfies the reliability requirements and is included in the next step of the research, which is the EFA exploratory factor analysis.

Table 4. Cronbach's Alpha Test Results of Transactional Leadership Style Variable

Cronbach's Alpha			Number of variables		
0.897			6		
Variable	Items	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed
GD1	The leader rewards employees for excellent performance.	18.08	11.979	0.656	0.889
GD2	The leader recognizes employees' efforts.	18.11	11.602	0.743	0.876
GD3	The leader closely monitors work and prevents errors.	17.96	11.626	0.728	0.878
GD4	The leader promptly handles signs of error.	18.12	11.704	0.694	0.883
GD5	The leader only intervenes when the problem is serious.	18.10	11.768	0.731	0.878
GD6	The leader is slow to respond to problems that arise.	18.02	11.318	0.781	0.870

Source: SPSS analysis results

Laissez-faire leadership style scale

According to Table 5, the Cronbach's Alpha test result of the transaction variable has a value of 0.786. According to the theory, the required Cronbach's Alpha value must be higher than 0.6 and less than 0.95, so the test value of the transaction variable has met the requirements. At the same time, the Cronbach's Alpha values

if the variable is eliminated are all less than 0.786, so no observed variables are eliminated. The test of the adjusted total correlation value of the variables all gave results greater than the minimum level of 0.3. Therefore, this scale satisfies the reliability requirements and is included in the next step of the research, which is the EFA exploratory factor analysis.

Table 5. Cronbach's Alpha Test Results for the Laissez-Faire Leadership Style Variable

Cronbach's Alpha			Number of variables		
0.786			2		
Variable	Items	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed
GD1	The leader gives little or no direction in the work.	10.93	3.358	0.625	0.716
GD2	The leader gives little or no direction in the work.	11.30	3.729	0.535	0.761

Source: SPSS analysis results

Employee satisfaction scale

According to Table 6, the Cronbach's Alpha test result of the transaction variable has a value of 0.827. According to the theory, the required Cronbach's Alpha value must be higher than 0.6 and less than 0.95, so the test value of the transaction variable has met the requirements. At the same time, the Cronbach's Alpha values

if the variable is eliminated are all less than 0.827, so no observed variables are eliminated. The test of the adjusted total correlation value of the variables all gave results greater than the minimum level of 0.3. Therefore, this scale satisfies the reliability requirements and is included in the next step of the research, which is the EFA exploratory factor analysis.

Table 6. Cronbach's Alpha Test Results of Employee Satisfaction Variables

Cronbach's Alpha			Number of variables		
0.827			2		
Variable	Items	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed	Scale mean if variable is removed Scale variance if variable is removed Item-total correlation corrected Cronbach's Alpha if variable is removed
HL1	I feel proud to work with my leader	11.11	2.018	0.717	0.754
HL2	I feel my leader has a positive influence on the organization	11.01	2.053	0.607	0.805
HL3	I feel satisfied with the way my leader manages	11.09	2.122	0.598	0.808
HL4	I will continue to participate with my	11.02	2.101	0.703	0.762

	leader on upcoming projects of the organization				
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Source: SPSS analysis results

Table 7. Summary of Cronbach's Alpha Test

Scale	Number of variables accepted	Cronbach's Alpha value	Eligibility	Evaluate
Transformational Leadership Style	6	0.891	0.6 ≤ Cronbach's Alpha ≤ 0.95	Meet the requirements for scale reliability
Transactional Leadership Style	6	0.897		
Laissez-faire leadership style scale	2	0.786		
Employee satisfaction	2	0.827		

Source: SPSS analysis results

Scale validation by exploratory factor analysis EFA

Exploratory factor analysis EFA with independent variables

Table 8. KMO and Bartlett's Test of Independent Variables

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin coefficient		0.721
Barlett's Test	Approx. Chi-Square	2273.450
	df	15
	Sig	0.000

Source: SPSS analysis results

According to Table 8, the test results show that the model data is suitable for the factor analysis methods used, so it can be affirmed that at least one pair of observed variables out of 15 observed variables in this analysis is related to each other, that is, its correlation matrix is not a unit matrix. Therefore, factor analysis is appropriate.

Exploratory factor analysis with dependent variable

The observed variables of the dependent variable employee satisfaction are HL1, HL2, HL3, HL4, the results of factor analysis are shown in the following table:

Table 9. KMO and Bartlett's Test of Dependent Variables

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin coefficient		0.768
Barlett's Test	326.337	2273.450
	6	223
	0.000	0.000

Source: SPSS analysis results

From table 9, it shows that the value: $0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$ and the Barlett's test value has $Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05$, therefore, factor analysis is appropriate.

Table 10. Summary of Representative Average Variables

Scale	Observation Variable	Observation Variable	Observation Variable
Transformational Leadership Style	CD1, CD2, CD3, CD4, CD5, CD6, CD7	CD	Independent Variable

Transactional Leadership Style	GD1, GD2, GD3, GD4, GD5, GD6	GD	Independent Variable
Laissez-faire leadership style scale	TD1, TD2	TD	Independent Variable
Employee satisfaction	HL1, HL2, HL3, HL4	HL	Dependent Variable

Source: SPSS analysis results

After factor analysis, the author calculates factor values based on the average value of observed variables belonging to each factor and this average value represents the observed variables in the following analyses.

Linear Regression Analysis

Results of correlation analysis between variables

Linear correlation analysis between the dependent variable satisfaction (HL) and each independent variable CD, GD, TD to demonstrate that there is a relationship between them and that the linear regression analysis in the next step is appropriate.

Table 6.11 shows that the correlation coefficient matrix of the independent variables CD, GD, TD all have a linear relationship with the dependent variable, specifically a positive correlation coefficient. The conversion variable CD has the highest correlation coefficient (0.652), followed by the transaction variable GD (0.609) and finally the free variable TD (0.377). All independent variables with the dependent variable have Sig coefficients less than 0.05, rejecting the hypothesis that there is no relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Table 11. Correlation Matrix Table

		HL	GD	CD	TD
HL	Pearson correlation	1	0.609	0.652	0.377
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.000
	N	224	224	224	224
GD	Trởng quan Pearson	0.609	1	0.284	0.97
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.162
	N	224	224	224	224
CD	Pearson correlation	0.652	0.284	1	0.214
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.002
	N	224	224	224	224
TD	Pearson correlation	0.377	0.097	0.214	0.048
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000
	N	224	224	224	224

Source: SPSS analysis results

From the correlation coefficient matrix, the author examines the relationship between independent variables. There are many variables with Sig coefficients less than 0.05. The author

suspects multicollinearity and conducts testing in the next step.

Linear regression analysis

Model fit assessment and verification

Table 12. Model Summary Table

Model	R	R ²	R ² correction	Durbin - Watson
1	0.820	0.672	0.665	2.116

Source: SPSS analysis results

Table 6.12 shows that the adjusted R² coefficient is 0.665, which means that the independent variables explain 66.5% of the variation in the

dependent variable, the rest is due to the influence of variables outside the model and random errors.

Table 13. ANOVA

Model		Total average	df	Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	30.290	3	7.573	103.841	0.000
	Residual	14.804	221	0.073		
	Total	45.093	224			

Source: SPSS analysis results

The F-test used in the ANOVA analysis table is a hypothesis test about the suitability of the linear regression model. Table 6.13 shows that the Sig value = 0.000, so the linear regression model is suitable for the population.

Determine the importance of variables in the model

Table 14. Regression Coefficient Results

Model		Unstandardized regression coefficients		Standardized regression coefficient	t	Sig.	Multicollinearity statistics	
		B	Standard deviation	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	Constant	0.514	0.160		3.217	0.002		
	GD	0.322	0.030	0.452	10.794	0.000	0.918	1.089
	CD	0.398	0.036	0.474	11.106	0.000	0.884	1.131
	TD	0.160	0.028	0.232	5.632	0.000	0.953	1.050

Source: SPSS analysis results

The regression results show that all independent variables have Sig values less than 0.05, all of these variables have an impact on employee satisfaction. The standardized regression coefficients of the independent variables all have regression coefficients $\beta > 0$, these factors have a positive impact on the satisfaction factor.

Table 6.14 shows that the CD factor has the greatest influence on the HL variable, followed by the GD variable, and finally the DC variable.

We have the following standardized regression equation:

$$HL = 0.452*GD + 0.474*CD + 0.232*TD$$

Evaluation of regression assumptions:

From the regression results table 6.14, it shows that the variance inflation factor VIF of the independent variables that are significant to the model is the lowest at 1.050 and the largest at 1.131, the model does not have multicollinearity, eliminating the suspicion of multicollinearity in the previous correlation analysis.

Hypothesis Testing

The research hypotheses on factors affecting employee satisfaction after testing are presented in the following table:

Table 15. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Content	Result
H1	Transformational leadership style has a positive effect on employee satisfaction at Vietnam Joint Stock Commercial Bank	Accept
H2	Transactional leadership style has a positive effect on employee satisfaction at Vietnam Joint Stock Commercial Bank	Accept
H3	The laissez-faire leadership style has a negative impact on employee satisfaction at Vietnam joint stock commercial banks.	Accept

Source: Author's synthesis

Conclusion

The study found that three leadership styles affect employee satisfaction in joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam. Of these, transformational leadership has the strongest impact on employee satisfaction. This result is reasonable for Vietnam's practice and is catching up with global trends as well as reasonable with some previous studies.

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